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The general description of the method used by the customs authorities in ensuring the economic security of the Republic of Kazakhstan

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Abstract. The article deals with the essence of economic security and issues related to the role of customs authorities and the methods and means used by them to ensure the economic security of the Republic of Kazakhstan. In fact, those disclosed link national and economic security, the main tasks and functions of customs service aimed to ensure the functioning of Effectiveness of Foreign Economic Relations and protect them from the effects of external destructive forces. Revealed some features of the main groups of tools and techniques that customs authorities provide economic security and protection of the economic interests of the state. And also, an attempt is made to analyze the norms of law provides for the implementation of measures prinaemyh state in this field.

Key words: National security, economic security, socio-economic system, foreign economic activity, customs activities, strategic directions, law enforcement, fiscal policy reform

Any State to its national security issue when relevant. Grows in the process of globalization of national security, especially on the issue of economic security is important: because it is the only one indicator of the level of development of the national economy. The most positive impact on the national economy of the process of globalization and its fight against the negative influence of the state action is carried out.

Economic security by strengthening the foundation of national security. The venerable politicians by saying that it is a tool for implementing protectionist policies, today the foundations of economic security, national security and national energy

attracts unexpected forward the importance of strengthening horizontal.

When the transformation of the socio-economic system, and will be the basis for the emergence of a specific crisis. And he, in turn, due to certain circumstances that the system poses no risk of extinction. Therefore, there is an issue of safety. This economic safety and provide support to the state and law is the basis for the improvement of the development of the concept of the state. Economic security is an integral part of national security.

Be among the top 30 most developed countries of the world on the strategic directions of development of the national economy in the world economy arrangement, based on the elimination of deficiencies in the production of the country's economic problems and to ensure the safety of the country's economic development.

The economic security of the Republic of Kazakhstan on the situation in the modern world of political parties, lawyers and economists' attention has become one of the most important problems. The condition of globalization of the world economy, the guarantor of the independence of the country's economic security of the country, is an important component of the national security of the Republic of Kazakhstan. When, ineffective and weak economy, elimination of internal and external threats, to ensure the safety of the country's military strong and mobile army may be difficult to hold the President of Kazakhstan, "Kazakhstan-2050 Strategy". Actual and predictable foreign policy and national interests and pointed out the main directions of strengthening regional and global security. They are:

1. Foreign policy modernization priorities.
2. The development of economic and trade diplomacy.
3. Regional security.
4. Global to contribute to the strengthening of security.
5. Strengthening national defense capacity and military doctrine found in the form of directions.

This includes all of the national interest.

This is the main message of the President as the basis of the quality of the country's economic development and the main priority of the initial explosion publication of Kazakhstan's successful integration into the international economy. Around the main functions of the main objectives of the customs authorities in order to facilitate trade and economic development of the country is carried out in the legal, economic and organizational measures [1].

1st Paragraph of the 6th article of the law of the Republic of Kazakhstan about "National Security" from 6th January 2012, in accordance with the national interests

of the state of implementation of human and civil rights, Kazakhstan society and the values associated with the ability to ensure the protection of the foundations of the constitutional system, the laws of the Republic of Kazakhstan recognized the political, economic, social and other needs that include a set [2].

As mentioned above, the economic security as an integral part of the national security of the country is one of the co-existence mechanism. Economic safety of the individual, society and the interests of the very existence of the state, as well as the global community to ensure development of the social economy of goods and services in the implementation of the expansion of the range of industrial and other facilities to have the opportunity to identify themselves and the nature of the internal and external security must include comprehensive protection of the state [3, p.32].

Economic security being examined in three aspects:

- as an integral part of national security;
- as an activity pursued in parallel with the protection of the economic interests of the country;
- as a goal or principle of the protection of the vital interests of the individual, society and the state.

This is an organizational and administrative method of economic management in the country as one of the key elements of economic reform, which the passage of the method is to improve the role of state regulation of foreign trade. Therefore, the effective economic regulation of the external tariff and non-tariff mechanism for efficient and uniform customs policy of the Republic of Kazakhstan, and the customs authorities to ensure the safety of the country's economic problems and to protect the interests of its economic situation.

Therefore, to ensure the economic security of the Republic of Kazakhstan is one of the priority tasks of the customs authorities. At the same time, the country's customs service and other types of security: border, environmental, financial, radiation, military, etc. engaged in the process to ensure their competence will be considered as one element of the government. This is determined by the voice of the customs control.

Moreover, national, international security and personal look at the three types of form, the customs authorities will take part in the process and to reduce the risk associated with all three levels.

On this occasion, the use of non-tariff regulation and in tariff mechanism in Kazakhstan customs policy and customs authorities to protect the economic interests of ensuring the economic security of the country and to agree on the conclusion of the

review [4, p. 3].

It should be noted that the concept of economic security includes not only the maintenance of a sufficient level of socio-political and military stability of the state, but, above all, economic development to include it in the processes of globalization taking place today in the world community.

Customs authorities play an important role in ensuring the economic security of the state. Participate in the regulation of foreign trade turnover with the customs authorities, as well as through the implementation of fiscal function, which supplements the state budget and thereby help to solve the economic problems of the country.

Protectionist measures to protect the state's production by the customs authorities. At present, the economy of the Republic of Kazakhstan After the open than before the economic security of the Republic of Kazakhstan was a real problem.

In accordance with the Article 7 of the Code of the Republic of Kazakhstan, one of the main principles of the foreign economic activity of the customs authorities and the customs of the persons carrying out activities in the field of rights, freedoms and legitimate interests of security.

And within the competency of the customs authorities to ensure that it is aimed at preserving one of the economic interests of the country will be the following:

1. The creation of the customs policy of the Republic of Kazakhstan to participate in its implementation;

2. The economic basis of the economic security of the Republic of Kazakhstan, which is within its competence;

3. protection of the economic interests of the Republic of Kazakhstan;

4. trade and economic relations of the customs regulation;

5. The customs taxes, duties, etc. customs duties;

6. The members of the movement of goods in the customs territory of the procedure;

7. contraband, violation of tax laws and customs procedures, through the customs border of narcotic substances, weapons, collected by the people of the Republic of Kazakhstan and foreign archeology, history, art objects, endangered animals and plants, etc. illegal trafficking of goods, as well as to assist in the fight against international terrorism;

8. Customs statistics of foreign trade strategy and special;

9. The state security, public order, health and lives of people, animals and plants, Kazakhstani goods imported from outside to assist in the implementation of measures to protect the interests of consumers;

10. The implementation of currency controls within its competence;

11. In order to fulfill the international obligations of the Republic of Kazakhstan, the Republic of Kazakhstan with respect to international agreements, customs and foreign countries, etc. Components authorities, international organizations dealing with the issues of customs, the implementation of the cooperation [5].

The customs authorities of the Republic of Kazakhstan within the framework of the implementation of the fiscal function of customs payments and taxes, as well as a special, anti-dumping and countervailing duties, and at the time of payment of the accuracy of their credit control and enforcement measures are being implemented.

Today, a significant portion of the income of the state budget on the basis of the customs due to the receipt of payments. Therefore, to ensure full payment of the proceeds of the strategic context of the customs authorities of the state's fiscal framework has identified the following main objectives:

Foreign economic activity participants to voluntarily create conditions which would allow increasing the share of customs payments in the following way:

work focused on how to identify the cause of the evasion of customs duties, taxes and fees applicable rights and responsibilities of participants in foreign economic activity rate, the powers of the customs authorities and their officials, as well as the customs administration to combat smuggling and actual results for the evasion of customs duties to increase awareness;

Participants of foreign economic activity more income to pay for their own customs revenues and a further increase in the share of customs payments in order to ensure improvement in the suppression of the facts of evasion of customs duties [6].

The main directions of development within the framework of the provision of security are to increase the effectiveness of law enforcement and customs control. This year, the customs authorities of the customs service competence analysis about the participation to ensure the security of the country, find a better view. The basis of the customs authorities, who plays in the international fight against smuggling offenses. Than the customs authority of this fiscal control and enforcement is a priority function is changing.

Customs Union since the last login was a large-scale beyond the boundaries of the country, including the security of the country. In accordance with the requirements of the Customs Union, the basic principle is the principle of sampling in the implementation of customs control, increasing the efficiency of the customs authorities of human rights defenders. Law enforcement violations of the customs authorities and crime detection,

warning, and the opening of the main directions of the investigation, the customs Meal Preference will be given to the purpose of the prevention of crimes and offenses [7, p. 78].

The customs authorities to ensure the safety of the country's economic activity related to the effectiveness of his methods and configurable. The customs authorities of the methods and means of ensuring the protection of the economic interests of the country will be divided into two main group:

1. Legal regulation of vehicles and methods of the Human Rights Defenders. In this case, the customs authorities with powers that allow you to prevent serious violations of law force, sanctions and enforcement measures. This group is the basis of the customs authorities of human rights defenders.

2. Foreign methods and means of regulating the relations of the state shall be subject to tariff and non-tariff regulation. Tariff regulation methods here: customs duties, taxes, and methods for the determination of the customs value, foreign exchange regulation, and methods to determine the country of origin, etc. includes. And tariff regulation: a ban on the import or release of goods, restrictions on the production and importation of goods, i.e., licensing, certification, and the establishment of a quota embargo (Latin for external economic relations, economic sanctions), etc. [4, p. 3].

Customs tariff is an important economic nature will be. Here it is a decision of an asset due to the economy and the market. Receive a share of the import tariff of customs regulation, the tax together with the owner; first of all, the price will affect the amount of business efficiency, as the national currency, the formation of the structure of the items, etc. regulatory assistance.

Import tariff counting process; Customs TP not only to determine the position of the product nomenclative as well as closely related to the method of determining the customs value.

Economic methods of regulation of foreign trade in the world are the tariff regulation. When they are crossing the border of the state, national and import flows contribute to the estimates. The main tariff regulation, the customs duties on goods and means of the procedure, as well as tax and tariff types, causes, customs privileges in order.

With the help of international organizations and associations and the border on the basis of bilateral agreements with many countries, national-tariff control system is based on the same principles and procedures, as well as, there are a lot of similarities between them, which facilitates international trade arcesin itself.

To activate the above directions a lot of changes in the taxation of the country of origin of the product and to remove the import customs tariff for inclusion in the active

part of the procedure is to determine the rate of customs duty. Export customs tariff regulation of foreign trade in only a few countries

Asia-based tool, mainly in developing countries. Rich in natural resources, but their raw materials are believed to hold the position in the market of the world. In some cases, the increase in export prices, as well as contributes to the development and replacement of its foreign exchange resources. However, restrictions on the export tariff change the structure of the volume of exports and export potential to reduce the domestic price will lead to inflationary pressure. In many countries, the development of the customs tariff of the following two methods: to increase the range of items and to a certain rate of more than one type of product.

The first method is called the common customs tariff. This product is to be at the same rate.

The second method for each product is the rate of two or more. This is due to their country. In the latter case, the high tariff rate is considered to be a stand-alone, it is called a tariff. There is marked goods tariff trade agreement and a contract between countries.

And the low, the convention or the minimum rate of the countries had positive order goods. Customs tariff in character as its economic meaning and foreign trade refers to the process of market regulation. Customs duty and tax as a product and as a set of crossing the country to other types of wealth tax. All other taxes, such as increases in the price of the goods or reduce its competitive abilities. Price restrictions by the customs tax is determined based on the level of customer groups and processing. Import customs tariffs to support the following goals:

- Adjust the influence of foreign goods in the domestic market;
- protection of domestic producers and to ensure the economic security of the country;
- stabilization of the economic situation in the country;
- internal and import of consumption of resources on the basis of rational economic structure;
- help with the restructuring of the national economy;
- business and political issues;

The maximum rate for most of the country's security is of strategic importance to ensure the self-production of the product is competitive industries or international scale.

Import duties minimum rated products produced in the country or at a level not higher is the country's industry leading products consumed in the field. At the present time, most of the developed countries of the customs duties for the import of raw

materials, the duties of finished products are set too high, and that stimulate domestic production to a great extent.

In most cases, domestic counterparts, and they will compete with imported goods. This should be determined by the ratios formed between costs and prices.

Between costs and prices of this product, can drift to a wide range of groups and types, and that the change in the rate of import duties on the type of product groups and the need to determine in advance.

When imported in large quantities and in a limited range of products imported into the country duty rates can be set for specific products.

Customs duties are important economic regulation of foreign economic activity, which is carried out by external economic exchange in the field of public policy, and therefore the degree of imported machinery and equipment and technical and not a natural state of inert or even obsolete and will not be able to create a natural preference for worn-out machinery. Actively related to foreign trade policy for the growth of export-import operations, resulting in an increase in the customs tariff regulation.

Foreign trade operations of the customs regulation plays an important role in the global economy, because the decrease in exports of goods and services in different countries, and can influence the actual growth.

Economic regulation of foreign trade in the world known to be the most important methods of customs and tariff regulation.

Customs tariff multilateral regulation. One of the most common in the world is a different system of preferences and privileges. This issue of customs and tax legislation of the Republic of Kazakhstan are regulated in detail. However, taking into account the rate of speed of economic development, it should be noted the need to improve the methods.

To improve the system of customs regulation in the Republic of Kazakhstan as a feature of the process of modernization of the modern model of the development of innovative approaches and advanced countries is reflected in the models used by the customs authorities of compatibility. This is to improve the competitiveness of the country and to be able to contribute to the economic development of stable and efficient service that allows for the creation of the customs system.

Light of what we have come to the end of the day, clarification of cause-and-effect relationships, flowing sequence of events to ensure economic security, the impact of various factors on these events provide an opportunity to define a conceptual model – a mechanism to ensure economic security. It is a theoretical justification for the sequence of events to ensure economic security. It's kind of a conditional way,

the circuit dynamics of economic security, including several coherent units. He is a theoretical map that represents the result of knowledge of the events and phenomena that occur in the real world.

Thus, taking into account the legal peculiarities of the national legislation of Kazakhstan, in our opinion, the mechanism of economic security – a system of legislative, organizational, legal, socio-economic, ideological, administrative, criminal law, informational, aimed at identifying, preventing and localization of threats to economic security of the Republic of Kazakhstan, the ongoing economic security of entities within the powers conferred on them by the current legislation of the Republic of Kazakhstan.

In addition, as noted above, to be used for the economic security of the customs authorities to ensure the protection of the economic interests of the state customs regulation, to ensure the effectiveness of trade-economic relations and to accelerate the process of its development, as well as stimulating the development of the national economy, external destructive forces to protect against the effects of legal, economic, organizational actions.

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